

Budgetary Process in Nigeria: A Critical Appraisal

Kingsley Osakpamwan, ENOBAKHARE

Department of Accounting
kingsley.enobakhare@uniben.edu

Alade Sule, OMOYE

Department of Accounting
alade.omoye@uniben.edu

Samuel Osarobo, OKUNROBO

Department of Accounting
osarobo.okunrobo@uniben.edu

Abstract

The budgetary process is very central to effective governance and the fiscal policy of any nation. In Nigeria, this process plays a crucial role in allocating resources and determining national priorities. The main objective of this paper is to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the budgetary process of the Nigeria government. The methodology adopted for the study is essentially a library survey involving the review of relevant literature, government documents and major institutional reports on the subject matter. The study's finding highlights the inefficiencies and systemic issues in the Nigeria budgetary process such as delays in the budgetary process, unrealistic revenue forecasting, political interference, incidence of budget padding, lack of transparency, minimal public participation in the budgeting process and pronounced implementation gap. The study also offers suggestions to improve the use of technology for transparency, fiscal discipline, institutionizing public participation, strengthening of legislative review, oversight, Medium Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) and reduction of unnecessary political inference in the budgeting process. The paper concludes by advocating for structural reforms to enhance Nigeria's budgetary framework because the activities of key budget actors to a large extent affects effective budget implementation and success in Nigeria.

Keywords: Budgetary Process, Effective Governance, Fiscal Discipline, Structural Reforms, Nigeria.

JEL Classification: H61, H83, H11

1. Introduction

Budgeting is a fundamental process in public finance management. It influences the economic policies and development trajectory of a country (Ojo & Aderemi, 2020). The modern national budget concept originated in the 18th Century Britain, when parliament began formally approving

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revenues and expenditures (Premchand, 2007; Wildavsky & Caiden, 2004). This usually took the form of the British Chancellor presenting annual financial statements to parliament for consideration and approval. This was closely followed by other countries like France, the United States and Japan who developed their formal budget law and budget offices in the 19th and early 20th Centuries (Schick, 1996; Wildavsky & Caiden, 2004) in line with the Britain pattern.

Modern budgeting practice in Nigeria is generally traced to 1928 when colonial administration presented the first annual budget (Aaron, 2003; Ola, 1990). This however became formalized and institutionalized after independence in 1960. The Nigerian budget is used by the government as a tool for resource allocation, economic management, performance evaluation and national development goals. Basically it is made up of two major parts: revenue and expenditure. It shows how the government tries to match its revenue with its expenditure. Each year, the government at all levels prepares budgets that reflect its fiscal priorities for the forthcoming fiscal year. The success or failure of such budget has direct implications for Nigeria's socio-economic growth.

In recent years, Nigeria's budgetary process has been criticized for being inefficient, opaque and fraught with excessive expenses. These issues have led to a misalignment between budgetary allocations and national development objectives (Aina & Olarewaju, 2021; International Monetary Fund [IMF], 2022). In other words, development in the country so far is not reflecting the huge budgetary outlay year in year out. Similarly IMF (2022) noted that the Nigeria government's continuous reliance on oil revenues, political interference and poor public sector accountability tend to further complicate the process.

The recurring budget deficits and poor execution of public projects have been a source of serious concern to researchers, corporate entities, Nigerian government and citizens. As it has led to multiple problems for all concerned in navigating the country's complex economy space on a daily basis. These issues result in fiscal imbalances, underfunding of critical sectors, and the inability to achieve stated national development goals. As Ojo and Aderemi (2020) pointed out, despite repeated reforms, the budgetary process continues to suffer from mismanagement, which tends to worsen the country's fiscal problems.

Tochukwu and Taofiq (2024) explored the relationship between political dynamics, budgeting process, development outcomes and identified key factors that influence budgetary decision in Nigeria. Clientelism, elite capture and corruption were identified as factors that significantly influence budget decisions that invariably hinder effective resource allocation for development. Ngara and Habila (2020), emphasized on the need for regular interface, synergy and cooperation between the executive and the leadership of the National Assembly at the highest level during budget consideration. This should be done in order to bridge communication gaps and then close ranks before the appropriation bill is formally presented. This they said, is to avoid misunderstanding and unnecessary conflicts and rancor that usually characterize the budget process that often leads to recurring delays in the passage of the appropriation act. Their work investigated particularly the role of one key budget actor that is the legislator in the Nigeria

budgetary process. There are however several other key actors such as the executive, legislature and judiciary in the budgetary process which this current paper addresses.

The 1999 Nigeria Constitution as amended makes the Executive and the Legislature the main actors in the budgetary process in Nigeria. For instance, sections 4, 59, 80 to 81 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, as amended, specifically detailed the powers and responsibilities of the two arms of Government on how monies accruing to the country may be expended over a period of time. Another actor in the budgetary process in Nigeria is the Civil Society of Nigeria (CSOs), though their role has been largely passive. The National Assembly in exercise of its power in sections 80 and 81 of the Constitution as amended is empowered to carry out oversight on the Executive arms of Government by ensuring that the provision of the Budget is complied with.

On the backdrop of the foregone discussion, it is clear that the continuous misalignment between Nigeria's massive annual budgetary allocations and actual socio-economic development stems from a flawed budgetary process characterized by inefficiency, opacity, corruption and structural dependencies (Aina & Olarewaju, 2021; Tochukwu & Taofiq, 2024). Despite repeated fiscal reforms, the public budgeting system remains severely compromised by elite capture, clientelism, political interference and an over-reliance on volatile oil revenue (IMF, 2022; Ojo & Aderemi, 2020). This systemic mismanagement manifests in recurring budget deficits, prolonged legislative delays due to executive-legislative rancor, passive civil society oversight and poorly executed public projects (Ngara & Habila, 2020). Consequently, these inefficiencies cause chronic fiscal imbalances and underfund critical sectors, directly hindering the country's ability to achieve its national development goals and worsening the economic challenges face by its citizens (Ojo & Aderemi, 2020).

While existing literature heavily concentrates on specific components such as legislative friction or political dynamics, there is a critical lack of comprehensive analysis regarding how all primary budget actors (the Executive, Legislature, Judiciary and Civil Society Organizations) interact under these constitutional and political pressures. This paper therefore took an in-depth appraisal of this budgetary process to identify the systemic weaknesses and made useful suggestions that would enhance fiscal discipline and hence improve public financial management.

Through review of relevant literature, government documents and institutional report on the subject matter this paper attempts to address the following identified research problems: (1) Are the provisions of the Constitution adequate to give Nigeria a functional Budget? (2) To what extent have the activities of the key budget actors affected effective budget implementation and success in Nigeria?

The rest of the paper is divided into 3 sections. Section 2 presents the literature review. Section 3 is on the findings and suggestions to improve the budgetary process in Nigeria, while section 4 is the concluding part of the paper.

2. Review of Literature

2.1. Public budgeting in Nigeria

A budget is a quantitative plan prepared for a specific time period. It is a financial plan that outlines the expected incomes and expenses for a defined period usually a year. Shah (2007) and Rubin (2001) as cited in Tochukwu and Taofiq (2024) suggest that government budgeting serves as a tool for fiscal management, as it allows governments to plan and control their spending, monitor revenue and achieve economic stability. It also plays a crucial role in resources allocation, ensuring that public funds are used efficiently and effectively to address societal needs and promote development. (Breton & Frascini, 2014; Shah, 2007). According to Keller and Ferrara (1966), a budget is a plan of action to achieve stated objectives based on predetermined series of related assumptions. In addition, IMF (2014) defines budget as a statement of government's financial plans, including its expected revenues, expenditures and financing over a specified period usually one year. In a nutshell, this paper operationally defines budget as a detailed financial plan that outlines an individual, organization's or government expected revenues and expenses over a specific period, usually one year. It serves as a tool for resources allocation, expenditure control and performance evaluation, ensuring that public funds are used efficiently and effectively to address societal needs and promote development.

Public budgeting is a structured process through which governments allocate financial resources to achieve their fiscal and policy objectives. It typically involves several stages of budget preparation, legislative approval, implementation, and evaluation (World Bank, 2021). The effectiveness of this process is often contingent upon the institutional frameworks in place, the accuracy of revenue forecasts, and the ability of government institutions to implement fiscal policies. This is one of the major differences between developed and developing Countries.

In developing economies such as Nigeria, weak institutions, political instability and corruption often tend to impede the effectiveness of budgetary processes (Akinyele, 2019). Fjeldstad et al. (2008), Swamy et al. (2001) as cited in Tochukwu and Taofiq (2024) held that corruption diverts public funds away from development priorities and foster rent-seeking behavior, where individuals and interest groups exploit budget process for personal gain. World Bank (2019, 2020, & 2021) posited that effective budgeting systems are critical for ensuring fiscal discipline, achieving macroeconomic stability, and enhancing government accountability.

The Nigerian budgetary process follows a presidential system in which the executive plays a key role. In Nigeria, the process begins with the drafting of the Medium Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) and Fiscal Strategy Paper (FSP), which provide the foundation for the annual budget. The Ministry of Finance, in conjunction with the Budget Office of the Federation, is responsible for preparing the budget. Following this, the budget is submitted to the National Assembly for review and approval.

Despite this structure, there are multiple challenges facing Nigeria's budget process, including late submission, unrealistic revenue estimates, and poor budget implementation (Ojo & Aderemi,

2020). Studies by the IMF (2022) indicate that these inefficiencies result in frequent budget deficits, inflation, and an overreliance on external borrowing.

2.2. Key budget actors and their roles in Nigeria

The Nigeria budgetary process is a multi-step procedure involving several key actors whose roles are defined by three statutory documents namely: the 1999 Constitution as amended, the Fiscal Responsibility Act (2007) and Established Public Finance Practice. These actors play significant roles at the various stages of the budgetary process starting from the formulation through approval, implementation to evaluation as well as oversight functions.

2.2.1. The Executive

This comprises the President, Federal Ministry of Finance, Budget Office of the Federation, National Planning Commission, Line Ministries, Department and Agencies (MDAs) as major players. They play a central role in budget preparation. The budgetary process begins with the formulation of the Medium Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) and the Fiscal Strategy Paper (FSP). The MTEF and FSP outline the government fiscal policy objectives, expenditure priorities and revenue projections for the next three years (IMF, 2022). The MTEF and FSP serve as a guide for Ministries, Departments, and Agencies (MDAs) in preparing their budget submissions. It also aims to enhance budget transparency, accountability and effectiveness in resource allocation. It is an important tool for improving fiscal discipline, budget planning and resource management in Nigeria (Budget office of Nigeria, 2023).

After the approval of the MTEF and FSP by the Federal Executive Council (FEC), the Ministry of Finance issues a Budget Call Circular to all MDAs, detailing expenditure ceilings and guidelines for budget preparation. Each MDA submits its budget proposals in line with these guidelines (Aina & Olunrewaju, 2021). These proposals are submitted to the Ministry of Finance and Budget office for consolidation. The Budget Office of the Federation consolidates the proposals from the MDAs into a draft national budget. This is the building block for Government annual budget proposal to the National Assembly. This draft is reviewed by the Minister of Finance and the President before it is presented to the National Assembly for approval (Ojo & Aderemi, 2020). The President's approval is required before the budget is submitted to the National Assembly.

2.2.2. The Legislature

This is the National Assembly comprising of the Senate and House of Representative. Their role is crucial in the review and amendment of the budget. They work mostly through their Committees on Appropriation and Finance as well as the Public Accounts Committee. The draft budget from the Executive Arm of Government is presented to the National Assembly, where it is subjected to debate and scrutiny. Legislative committee reviews the budget in detail, and amendments may be made to reflect the interest of the legislative body. Akinyele, (2019) observes that, this stage is often the most contentious and it is where delays frequently occur, as lawmakers seek to influence the budget for political purposes. This is primarily as a result of political interest as political gladiators tries to twist the budget to the favour of their geopolitical

zone or party interest as the case may be. The legislators' input makes the budgetary process very robust. Legislators as democratically elected officials, not only make laws and represent their political parties and constituencies, they also make critical inputs to the budgetary process. This is a key functional duty of a Nigerian legislator.

Once the National Assembly approves the budget, it is signed into law by the President, and implementation can begin. It should however be noted that Senate and the House of Representative must pass the same version of the Budget (or MTEF) for it to qualify for the President's assent. According to section 187 of the Fiscal Responsibility Act, 2007 in the event of a disagreement between the houses of National Assembly, the joint Committee on Appropriation will refer both versions of passed bills to the Conference Committee for harmonization and Concurrence. This Committee is usually made up of equal number of Senators and members of the House of Representatives. However, late passage of the budget often results in delayed implementation which invariably impacts on the execution of the government projects (IMF, 2022).

2.2.3. The Judiciary

The judiciary arm interprets budget-related laws and constitutional provisions. This they do by adjudicating disputes arising from budget implementation, public finance and enforcing compliance with fiscal law. They also support the work of anti-corruption agencies such as EFCC, ICPC through enforcement of Accountability and Anti-Corruption laws sanctioning offenders to deter financial crime. The judiciary plays a crucial oversight role in Nigerian's budgetary process by interpreting fiscal laws, enforcing constitutional compliance and adjudicating budget related disputes.

Recent studies show that interpretation of Appropriation Act and Fiscal Responsibility Act enhances legality and discipline in public expenditure, thereby preventing unauthorized spending by the executive (Adeleke & Ojo, 2022). Through the enforcement of anti-corruption laws and protection of judicial financial autonomy, the judiciary tends to strengthen accountability and transparency in Nigeria's budgetary system (Ibrahim & Garuba, 2023; Okeke & Yusuf, 2021).

2.2.4. External and non-state actors

This comprises the Civil Society Organization (CSO), Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) and the Media. They perform the informal role of holding Government to Account for how they manage public funds which is only possible when meaningful opportunities exist for them to participate in the budgetary process. This they do by promoting transparency, accountability, public participation and effective use of public funds. They demand access to budget documents, using the freedom of information (FOI) Act. Good examples of this in Nigeria are BudgIT, SERAP, CISLAC, PPDC, Yiaga Africa etc. Their roles cut across the pre-budget, budget approval, implementation and monitoring.

CSOs and NGOs have become key actors in Nigeria's budgetary process, particularly in promoting transparency and Accountability as mentioned before. Studies show that these organizations engaged in budget advocacy, citizen mobilization and expenditure tracking to

reduce corruption and improve service delivery (Eze & Nwankwo, 2021). Similarly NGOs contribute to pro-poor budgeting by influencing sectoral allocations and monitoring implementation outcomes (Adebayo & Omotola, 2020). The media compliment these efforts by acting as a watchdog and facilitating public debate on budgetary issue (Ojebode, 2020). The enactment of freedom of information Act has strengthened the capacity of civil society groups and the media to demand budget transparency and hold public official accountable (Agba et al., 2022).

The International Budget Partnership, Open Budget survey of 2023 report scored Nigeria 31 out of 100 for budget transparency and 19 out of 100 for public participation, highlighting significant gaps in public access to budget information and citizens' engagement (International Budget Partnership, 2023). The same survey shows that global average score is 45 out of 100 and 15 out of 100 for public participation.

Like the development partners, international institutions such as the World Bank, International Monetary Funds and African Development Bank play some indirect roles in the budgetary process in Nigeria. For instance, they provide technical assistance, budget support as well as promoting transparency and fiscal reforms. The private sector on the other hand bids for Government contracts. So, they are also key players in the budgetary process. They execute government contracts, projects, influences fiscal policy through investment and taxation.

2.3. Key Provisions of the Constitution on Budgeting

The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended) contains several core provisions governing public budgeting, public finance and fiscal accountability. These provisions are explained below:

Sections 80-85 of the Constitutions provide the primary legal framework for federal budgeting by mandating that all revenues be paid into the Consolidated Revenue Funds (CRF) and prohibiting withdrawals without legislative authorization (FRN, 1999). These provisions reflect classical public finance principles that emphasize legislative control over public expenditure as a safeguard against executive dominance (Schick, 1998). Allen and Tommasi (2001) argued that a sound public expenditure management system must be grounded in legal and institutional arrangements that allocate clear financial responsibilities and authorities between the executive and the legislature. They emphasized that Budget approval and authorization of expenditure are core legislative functions, designed to ensure accountability and prevent discretionary or arbitrary spending by the executive.

Section 81 further requires the President to present annual estimates of revenue and expenditure to the National Assembly, thereby institutionalizing the annual budget as a central instrument of fiscal governance. This provision formally aligns the budgeting process with the doctrine of separation of powers, assigning the legislature a decisive role in authorizing public spending (Akindele & Olaopa, 2002).

Section 80 and 81 empower the National Assembly to authorize expenditures through Appropriation Acts, while section 59 outlines the procedures for passing money bills. These provisions reflect international norms that regard parliaments as key institutions for ensuring fiscal accountability and transparency (OECD, 2015). Omitola and Saliu (2009) are of the view that though Nigeria's legislature arm of governance possesses strong constitutional budgetary powers, institutional capacity constraints and political dynamics often tends to weaken its ability to scrutinize executive proposals.

Sections 82 and 83 of the Constitution permit limited executive spending in absence of an approved Appropriation Act and authorize the use of Contingencies fund for urgent and unforeseen expenditures. From a public financial management perspective, such provisions are designed to ensure continuity of government operations while maintaining legislative supremacy (Premchand, 1999). Recent studies have however shown that contingency spending often undermines fiscal institutions (Allen et al., 2017). This risk is compounded in Nigeria by delays in budget passage and limited enforcement of reporting requirements.

Section 85 of the Constitution establishes the office of the Auditor-General for the Federation which mandates the audit of public accounts and submission of audit reports to the National Assembly. This provision aligns with international standards that emphasized the independence of Supreme Audit Institutions as prerequisite for effective public finance accountability INTOSAI, (2019).

Nigeria's constitutional audit framework is relatively strong in design but weak in implementation. Adegite (2010), Malgwi and Unegbu (2012) note persistent delays in audit reporting, limited legislative follow-up and weak enforcement of audit recommendations. These challenges reflect a broader pattern observed in many developing countries where constitutional audit mandates are undermined by political inference and institutional capacity gaps (de Renzio & Masud, 2011).

2.4. Budgetary Processes in Selected Countries

A comparative analysis of Nigeria's budgetary process with those of other countries offers some insights into best practices that can enhance efficiency, transparency, and promote inclusiveness. This section therefore examines budgetary processes in some selected highly industrialized countries such as the United States, the United Kingdom, and then South Africa which is also a developing economy like Nigeria, by highlighting similarities, differences, and lessons which Nigeria can adopt or adapt for improvement. Though these countries used for comparison may not have the same system of Government with Nigeria, their approach to budgeting is what is of interest to this study.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Budgetary Process using International Best Practice for Nigeria, United State, United Kingdom and South Africa.

Dimension	International Best Practice	Nigeria	United States	United Kingdom	South Africa
Legal and Institutional Framework	Budgeting governed by constitution and fiscal responsibility legislation, supported by independent institutions	Constitutional provisions and Fiscal Responsibility Act exist, but enforcement remains weak.	Robust statutory framework under the Congressional Budget Act and OMB regulations.	Strong legal and institutional tradition under Finance Acts and Treasury rules	Constitution and Public Finance Management Act (PFMA) provide a strong legal basis.
Budget Time Horizon	Annual budget embedded within a medium term (3-5 years) fiscal framework.	Annual budgeting supported by an MTEF, though weakly linked to actual allocations.	Predominantly annual budgeting with limited medium term orientation.	Annual budget complemented by multi-year Spending Review.	Annual budgeting fully integrated within a Medium Term Expenditure Framework
Budget Formulation	Executive prepares the budget based on credible macro-economic forecasts and policy priorities	Executive-led formulation often based on optimistic revenue projections	Executive (President and OMB) prepares comprehensive budget proposals	Executive (Chancellor and HM Treasury) prepares budget.	Executive (National Treasury) prepares budget within expenditure ceilings.
Legislative Scrutiny and Approval	Legislature exercises meaningful review, amendment and approval through committees and hearing	National Assembly reviews and amends budgets, often influenced by political bargaining.	Congress exercises strong amendment and oversight authority.	Parliament securitizes the budget with limited amendment power.	Parliament reviews, amend and approves the budget.
Timeliness of Budget Approval	Budgets are approved prior to the commencement of the fiscal year	Frequent delays in passage, leading to late implementation.	Delays common due to partisan deadlock	Generally approved on schedule	Usually timely, though occasional delay occur
Medium Term Fiscal Planning	Medium-term planning central to fiscal discipline and expenditure control.	MTEF exists but weakly enforced.	No formal MTEF structure	Implemented through Spending Reviews.	Strongly institutionalized through the MTEF.
Public Participation	Institutionalized citizen and civil society engagement during formulation and approval.	Limited and largely procedural participation.	Limited, mainly through congressional hearings	High levels of public debate and transparency.	Formal mechanisms for public input exist.
Budget Transparency	Comprehensive and timely publication of budget documents	Transparency remains limited and inconsistent.	High levels of transparency.	High level of transparency.	Relatively high transparency.

	and reports				
Budget Execution and Control	Expenditures executed in line with approved appropriations and strict financial controls.	Weak execution, especially in capital expenditure.	Strong execution under OMB supervision.	Strong execution under HM Treasury control.	Strong execution, though administrative capacity varies.
Audit and Accountability	Independent supreme audit institutions reports to the legislature.	Auditor General exists but sanctions are weak	Strong independent oversight by GAO and Inspectors General.	National Audit office provides strong oversight.	Auditor General enjoys constitutional independence.
Fiscal Discipline.	Clear rules governing deficits, debts and expenditure ceilings.	Fiscal rules frequently breached.	Rules exist but subject to political negotiation.	Fiscal rules guide budget discipline.	Fiscal discipline enforced through Treasury oversight.
Digital Transparency Platforms	Aligning with international benchmarks – Open budget survey (OBS), International Budget Partnership (IBP), Global Initiative for Fiscal Transparency (GIFT), Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD)	Civic tech tools by organizations like BudGIT: Tracka for project implementation at Community level, GovSpend to monitor federal releases and contract recipients. Open budget documents and LG Alerts for Local Government funds.	USAspending.gov offers public accessible dashboards and a spending explorer to track federal outlays by category, agency, geography	Open data platform data.gov.uk provides non-personal government dataset, including financial and budgetary figures crucial for public analysis.	Vaulekamali offers national/provincial budget and actual expenditure data with educational resources and civil engagement features. Municipal Money visualizes municipal budgets and financial performances for Citizens.
Overall Alignment with Best Practice.		Low to Moderate.	High	High	Moderate to High.

Source: Author's compilation based on IMF, OECD, World Bank, International Budget Partnership and National Budgetary Frameworks.

From Table 1, the comparative analysis reveals significant variation in the alignment with international best practices in budgetary governance. While the United States and the United Kingdom demonstrate high levels of institutionalization, transparency and legislative oversight, their systems are immuned to political contestation, particularly in the timing of budget approval. South Africa exhibits strong adherence to medium-term fiscal planning and legal oversight,

consistent with international norms, although political dynamics occasionally affect implementation. Nigeria, by contrast, displays a pronounced implementation gap, despite the existence of formal legal and institutional frameworks, persistent delays, weak enforcement of fiscal rules and limited transparency undermine the effectiveness of the budgetary process.

These findings underscore the importance of strong and functional formal institutional design as well as sound enforcement capacity and political commitment in achieving sound budgetary process in Nigeria.

2.4. Challenges of Budgetary Process in Nigeria

2.4.1 Delays

Delays in the Nigeria budgetary process are recurrent issues. Despite constitutional provisions mandating the submission of the budget before the start of a new fiscal year, it is frequently submitted late by the executive, leading to delays in legislative review and approval. These delays tend to disrupt the effective implementation of government programs and projects, often pushing back the execution of critical infrastructure and social services. There is usually delay in at least one of these stages of the budgetary process year in year out. For instance, the implementation of the capital budget for the past four years was allowed to carry over and remain active into the following years. For instance, the 2022 budget remained active till 31st March 2023; the 2023 budget until 30th June 2024 and the 2024 budget remain active until 31st December 2025 while the 2025 budget is to remain active until 30th November, 2026.

2.4.2. Unrealistic revenue forecasting

Nigeria's budgetary process is heavily reliant on revenue projections from oil, which constitutes a major portion of the source of the Country's income. Therefore, volatility in global oil prices frequently leads to discrepancies between projected and actual revenues, resulting in budget shortfalls as observed by Aina and Olanrewaju (2021). For instance, the 2020 budget had to be revised due to a drastic fall in oil prices caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Poor forecasting also affects the allocation of resources to non-oil sectors, creating an imbalanced fiscal policy. This is one of the major causes of Nigeria's high debt profile, driven by the nation's continuous internal and external borrowing.

2.4.3. Political interference and budget padding

Buhari, according to Punch, (2018), then President of Nigeria lamented that Political interference in Nigeria's budgetary process is a significant challenge, accusing lawmakers of frequent "budget padding" – the insertion of extraneous, unapproved expenditures for personal or political gain. This thus leads to a situation where the budget is compromised. The competition for constituency projects among legislators is a good example of political interference which often delays budget approval and distort national priorities. This practice undermines the integrity of the budget process and results in inefficient resource allocation to national priorities areas.

2.4.4. Lack of transparency and public participation

The level of transparency and public participation in Nigeria budgetary process is still very low. Although the Open Budget Survey (2021) indicates some improvements in budget transparency, public participation in the early stages of the process still remains minimal and weak. For instance, civil society organizations and citizens are often excluded from crucial stages of budget formulation: thus limiting opportunities for public oversight, input and accountability.

3. Suggestions to Improve Budgetary Process in Nigeria

While the Nigerian government has made significant efforts to streamline the budgetary process, persistent challenges such as delayed budget approval, revenue shortfalls, and limited public engagement still hinder the effectiveness of the process. Based on the analyses presented in this paper so far, the following suggestions are proposed to improve Nigeria's budgetary process.

3.1. Institutionalize public participation in the budget process

Increasing public involvement in the budgetary process can enhance transparency, accountability, and alignment with citizen needs. To achieve this, the government should engage in more and wider public consultations. In this respect, the Nigeria government should conduct more and wider public consultations before drafting the budget. For instance, civil society organizations, industry groups and citizens should be engaged at an early stage as they can provide valuable feedback on budget priorities thereby making the process more inclusive.

Simplification of Budget Documents should be encouraged. Budget documents are often technical and inaccessible to the general public. Simplifying these documents and making them publicly available will encourage greater participation and allow citizens to hold the government accountable.

Technology should be utilized for Public Engagement. The use of digital platforms for budget participation, similar to USASpending.gov in the United States as well the UK Public spending website in use in United Kingdom can enhance citizens' involvement. Nigeria should improve the functionality of the Open Treasury Portal by making it more user-friendly and allowing for public input throughout the cycle.

3.2. Strengthen legislative review and oversight

The National Assembly plays a critical role in approving the budget, but delays in the review process often impact timely implementation. To address this, improvement of parliamentary efficiency should be pursued. In this regards, Nigeria's legislature should streamline its internal processes for budget review, reducing delays caused by prolonged committee hearings. This can be achieved by setting clear timelines for each stage of the review process and improving coordination between the executive and legislative branches.

Political Interference should be prevented. Legislative interference, particularly in the form of budget padding, undermines fiscal discipline. A situation where every member of the National Assembly wants to site a public institution in his or her domain (constituency) should be curtailed. Institutional reforms are necessary to limit discretionary changes during the legislative

review process. Transparency mechanisms should be put in place to ensure that all amendments are in line with national priorities.

3.3. Expand the use of technology for transparency

While Nigeria has made commendable efforts with the Open Treasury Portal. Further technological integration can enhance transparency and accountability in the budget process: like Real-Time Budget Tracking. The Nigeria government should therefore expand the Open Treasury Portal to allow for real-time tracking of budget implementation, similar to models in the United States and South Africa. Citizens should be able to monitor how and where government funds are being spent. This will enable the citizens to see when a project is advertised, contract awarded and payment made for the project on completion. A good way of doing this is by aligning the procurement plan of the Country with its budget as obtainable in South Africa.

There is also the need for budget integration with the MTEF. The Open Treasury Portal should also include detailed information about the MTEF, making it easier for the public to track budget priorities over the medium term. This way, real-time tracking of government expenditure will be easy to follow. This will improve public understanding of long-term fiscal planning.

3.4. Strengthen the medium-term expenditure framework (MTEF)

The MTEF provides an opportunity for Nigeria to align her annual budget with its long-term development goals. However, its implementation has faced challenges, particularly in the area of consistency and adherence to fiscal targets. To improve the MTEF, there is need for a better alignment with development plans as obtainable in United Kingdom and South Africa. The MTEF should be closely aligned with Nigeria's national development plans, such as Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP) – (2017-2020) launched during the final year of the administration of President Muhammadu Buhari and the Vision 2020 document launched in 2009. The United Kingdom's Comprehensive Spending Review and South Africa's alignment with their National Development Plan underscore the importance of multi-year budgeting. Nigeria's Medium-Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) could be strengthened with more rigorous planning and better execution to improve fiscal discipline. This will ensure that budget allocations are consistent with the country's long-term national/strategic development goals as obtainable in the above mentioned countries.

The enforcement mechanisms should be strengthened. The MTEF should be enforced more rigorously, with strict adherence to revenue and expenditure ceilings. The National Assembly and the Ministry of Finance should collaborate to ensure that the MTEF is not altered arbitrarily during the budget process.

3.5. Enhance non-oil revenue mobilization

Nigeria's heavy reliance on oil revenues makes its budget vulnerable to global price fluctuations, often leading to revenue shortfalls. Nigeria should diversify its revenue base by reducing its dependency on oil revenues, consistent internal/external borrowing and enhancing non-oil

revenue sources. This can be done by diversifying the revenue sources. Beyond oil, Nigeria must prioritize the development of non-oil sectors, such as agriculture, manufacturing, solid minerals, tourism and services to create more stable revenue streams. The current tax reforms should be sustained to improve the efficiency of tax collection and expansion of the tax base. The government should also focus on enabling policies that attract foreign investments and boost domestic production.

4. Summary and Conclusion

Modifying Nigeria's budgetary process is critical for improving fiscal discipline, transparency, and the overall effectiveness of public spending. However, inefficiencies, delays, political interference, irregular interface and weak synergy/cooperation between the executive and the leadership of the National Assembly have hindered its effectiveness. Furthermore, the study observes that Nigeria Constitution contains robust provisions comparable to best practices in advanced economies. The main challenge however stems from the activities of key budget actors which undermine institutional effectiveness and hinder budgetary process, especially during budget preparation, review and implementation.

Having evaluated the structure and challenges of the Nigerian budgetary process, the study proposed suggestions for improvement. The adoption of these suggestions of institutionalizing public participation in the budgetary process, strengthening legislative review and oversight, expanding the use of technology for transparency and strengthening the MTEF can create a more accountable and inclusive budget process. These reforms will also help ensure that the Nigeria government's fiscal policies are aligned with national development goals and that public resources are used effectively for the benefits of all citizens.

Conclusively, it is clear that the actions of key budget actors largely determine the effectiveness and success of the budgetary process in Nigeria. A well-executed budgetary process serves as a catalyst for economy development as demonstrated by the budgetary practices of the United States of America, United Kingdom and South Africa.

REFERENCES

- Aaron, K.K (2003). Perspectives on the Nigerian budget process. *Nigeria Journal of Public Administration*, 36, (2), 45-60.
- Adebayo, A.A., & Omotola, J.S. (2020). Non-governmental organization and pro-poor budgeting in Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research*, 12(3), 89-102.
- Adeleke, A. A. & Ojo, E.O (2022). Constitutionalism and public expenditure control in Nigeria. *Africa Journal of Public Administration*, 12 (1), 33 -49.
- Adepoju, A. A., & Oladeji, T. S. (2021). Incremental budgeting in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects *Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research*, 13(2), 51-59.

- Agba, M.S., Akwara, A.F., & Idu, A.Y. 2022. Freedom of information and fiscal transparency in Nigeria's public sector. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 45(6), 421-435.
- Aina, O., & Olanrewaju, F. (2021). Fiscal Policy and Budgeting in Nigeria: A Critical Analysis *Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research*, 13(2), 45-60.
- Akindele, S.T., Olaopa, O.R., & Obiyan, A.S (2002). Fiscal federalism and local government finance in Nigeria: An examination of revenue right and fiscal jurisdiction. *International Review of Administrative Sciences* (68(4), 557-577.
- Akinyele, R. (2019). Principal-Agent Problems in Public Sector Budgeting: A Case Study of Nigeria. *African Journal of Economics and Development Studies*, 5(3), 20-35.
- Allen, R.I., Chaponda, T., Fisher, L., & Ray, R. 2017. Medium-term budget frameworks in sub-sahara Africa Counties (IMF Working Paper No.17/203). International Monetary Fund.
- Allen, R., & Tommasi, D. (Eds.). (2001). Managing public expenditure: A reference book for transition countries. OECD Publishing.
- Breton, A., & Fraschini, A. (2014). Public Sector Economics and the need for reforms Routledge.
- Buchanan, J. M., & Tullock, G. (1962). The Calculus of Consent: Logical Foundations of Constitutional Democracy. University of Michigan Press.
- Budget office of the federation, Nigeria (2023, October 24). Understanding the draft 2024-2026 Medium-Term Expenditure framework & fiscal strategy paper. Budget office of the federation.
- Cabinet Office. (2011). The Cabinet Manual.
- De Renzio, P., & Masud, H. (2011). Measuring and promoting budget transparency: The open Budget Index as a research and advocacy tool. *Governance: An International Journal of Policy, Administration, and Institutions*, 24(3), 607-616.
- Ejiofor, E. A., & Ayogu, D. U. (2019). Agency theory and budgetary control in public sector accounting. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 21(1), 102-116.
- Emeh, O. I., & Onwuka, E. C. (2019). Public Choice Theory and the Challenge of Budget Implementation in Nigeria. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(2), 45-58.
- Eze, F.O & Nwankwo, C.F. (2021). Civil Society participation and budget accountability in Nigeria. *Africa Journal of Government and Development*, 10(2), 45-60.
- Fiscal Responsibility Act, 2007, Section 187 (Nigeria).

- Fjeldstad, O.H., Isaksen, J., & Rakner, L. (2008). Corruption in tax administration: Lessons from institutional reforms in Uganda. *World Development*, 36(11), 2313-2327.
- Fourie, M., & Burger, P. (2017). Fiscal Transparency and Participation in South Africa's Budget Process. *African Journal of Public Affairs*, 9(4), 15-30.
- Ibrahim, M., & Garuba, H.A. (2023)., Judicial accountability and anti-corruption enforcement in Nigeria's Public Sector. *International Journal of Public Law and Policy* 9(1), 56-72.
- Iloh, E.C & Nwokedi M.E (2016). Budget Process and Participating Budgeting in Nigeria Lessons from Latin America.
- International Budget Partnership (2023). Open Budget Survey 2023: Nigeria Country Result.
- International Monetary Fund (2022). Fiscal Transparency Evaluation: *Nigeria*. Washington, D.C.: International Monetary Fund.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs, and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305-360.
- Keller, I.W., & Ferrara, W.L (1966). Management accounting for profit control (2nd ed.). McGraw.Hill.
- Khan, A., & Hildreth, W. (2022). Budgeting and Financial Management for Public Managers. Routledge.
- Malgwi, A.A., & Unegbu, A.O. (2012). Budgeting in Nigeria public sector: Need for balanced scorecard perspective. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*. 1(2), 1-6.
- Ngara, C.O & Daset H.K (2020). The Role of National Assembly in Budget Process in Nigeria. *Nilds Journal of Democrtic Studies*. 1, 1-17.
- Nigeria. (1999). Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended). Abuja: Federal Government Printer.
- Nigerian Ministry of Finance, Budget, and National Planning. (2022). 2022 Budget Circular.
- Ojebode, A. (2019). Media accountability and public finance management in Nigeria. *Journal of Africa Media Studies*. 11 (1) 23-38.
- Ojo, T., & Aderemi, A. (2020). Challenges of Budget Implementation in Developing Economies: Evidence from Nigeria. *African Journal of Public Administration*, 12(1), 52-69.

- Okeke, D. O., & Umeadi, I. (2017). The Nigerian budget process: Challenges and reforms. *Journal of African Studies and Development*, 9(5), 46-57.
- Okeke, C.N., & Yusuf, S.A. (2021) judicial financial autonomy and democratic governance in Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Constitutional Law*, 6(2), 101-118.
- Okonkwo, P. O., & Obaji, O. (2020). Oil dependency and the Nigerian budget: A resource dependence theory approach. *African Journal of Economic Review*, 8(2), 1-20.
- Okwoli, A. A. (2019). Medium-Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) as a budgetary tool in Nigeria. *Public Finance Quarterly*, 10(2), 87-102.
- Ola, C.S (1990) Budgeting and budgetary control in government. Amfitop Books
- Olomola, P. A. (2021). Fiscal Responsibility and Budgetary Reforms in Nigeria: Progress and Prospects. *Journal of Public Administration*, 14(2), 89-105.
- Omolehinwa, E. O., & Naiyeju, J. K. (2019). Budgeting and budgetary control in Nigerian public sector. *Journal of Governmental Financial Management*, 68(1), 26-39.
- Omotola, J.S., Saliu, H. (2009). Foreign aid, debt relief and Africa's development: Problems and prospects. *South African Journal of International Affairs*, 16(1), 87-102.
- Open Budget Survey (2021). Nigeria Country Report. Washington, D.C.: International Budget Partnership.*
- Open Treasury Portal. (2023). *Treasury Transparency Report.*
- Premchand, A.(1999). Public financial management: Getting the basics right. In S.Schiavo-Campo (Ed.), *Governance corruption, and public financial management* (PP.47-88). *Asian Development Bank.*
- Premchand, A. (2007). *Government budgeting and expenditure management: Principles and International practice.* International Monetary fund.
- Punch Editorial Board. (2018, June 27). National Assembly's incessant budget padding. *Punch Newspapers.*
- Republic of South Africa. (1999). *Public Finance Management Act of 1999.* Government Gazette.
- Republic of South Africa. (2003). *Municipal Finance Management Act 56 Of 2003.* Government Gazette.

Republic of South Africa. (2024). Division of Revenue Act 5 of 2024. Government Gazette. <https://www.voafrica.com>nigeria>.

Rubin, I.S. (2001). Handbook of budgeting (5th ed). John Wiley & Sons.

Rubin, I. (2019). The Politics of Public Budgeting: Getting and Spending, Borrowing and Balancing. CQ Press.

Schick, A. (1966). The road to PPB: The stages of budget reform. *Public Administrative Review*, 26 (4), 243-258.

Schick, A. (1998). A Contemporary approach to public expenditure management. World Bank Institute.

Schick, A. (2013). The Federal Budget: Politics, Policy, Process. Brookings Institution Press.

Shah, A.(2007). Fiscal decentralization and fiscal performance. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper No. 3922.

Swamy, A., Knack, S., Lee, Y., & Azfar, O. (2001). Gender and Corruption. *Journal of Development Economics*, (64 (1), 25-55.

Tochukwu S. Ezeudu & Taofiq James Fadeyi: *Journal of Public Administration* Vol.6, Issue 1 (2024).

UK Paliament. (2000). Government Resources and Account Act 2000.

UK Paliament. (2011). Budget Responsibility and National Audit Act. 2011.

Wildavsky, A., & Caiden, N. (2004). The new politics of budgetary process (5th ed.) Pearson Longman.

World Bank (2019). Nigeria public financial management assessment. PEFA Performance Report.

World Bank (2020). Enhancing public financial management in Africa. World Bank Africa Regional Report.

World Bank (2021). Public Sector Budgeting and Accountability in Developing Countries. Washington, D.C.: World Bank.